

Calibration and Uncertainty for multiRater Volume Assessment in multiorgan Segmentation 2nd Edition: Structured description of the challenge design

CHALLENGE ORGANIZATION

Title

Use the title to convey the essential information on the challenge mission.

Calibration and Uncertainty for multiRater Volume Assessment in multiorgan Segmentation 2nd Edition

Challenge acronym

Preferable, provide a short acronym of the challenge (if any).

CURVAS - PDACVI

Challenge abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In medical imaging, DL models are often tasked with delineating structures or abnormalities within complex anatomical structures, such as tumors, blood vessels, or organs. Uncertainty arises from the inherent complexity and variability of these structures, leading to challenges in precisely defining their boundaries. This uncertainty is further compounded by interrater variability, as different medical experts may have varying opinions on where the true boundaries lie. DL models must grapple with these discrepancies, leading to inconsistencies in segmentation results across different annotators and potentially impacting diagnosis and treatment decisions. Addressing interrater variability in DL for medical segmentation involves the development of robust algorithms capable of capturing and quantifying uncertainty, as well as standardizing annotation practices and promoting collaboration among medical experts to reduce variability and improve the reliability of DL-based medical image analysis. Interrater variability poses significant challenges in the field of DL for medical image segmentation.

This challenge is designed to promote awareness of the impact uncertainty has on clinical applications of medical image analysis. In our last-year edition, we proposed a competition based on modeling the uncertainty of segmenting three abdominal organs, namely kidney, liver and pancreas, focusing on organ volume as a clinical quantity of interest. This year, we go one step further and propose to segment pancreatic pathological structures, namely Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC), with the clinical goal of understanding vascular involvement, a key measure of tumor resectability. In this above context, uncertainty quantification is a much more challenging task, given the wildly varying contours that different PDAC instances show.

This year, we will provide a richer dataset, in which we start from an already existing dataset of clinically verified contrast-enhanced abdominal CT scans with a single set of manual annotations (provided by the PANORAMA organization, which we invite to be part of our challenge), and make an effort to construct four extra manual

annotations per PDAC case. In this way, we will assemble a unique dataset that creates a notable opportunity to analyze the impact of multi-rater annotations in several dimensions, e.g. different annotation protocols or different annotator experiences, to name a few.

Challenge keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the challenge.

Abdominal CT, Uncertainty Quantification, Multi-Rater Annotations, Segmentation, PDAC, Vascular Involvement

Year

2025

Novelty of the challenge

Briefly describe the novelty of the challenge.

No previous competition has focused on assessing uncertainty in Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC) segmentation. In addition, no previous challenge has dealt with vascular involvement, a clinically-relevant biomarker related to tumor resectability, and there exists no previous dataset with a similar amount of multi-rater annotations for PDAC segmentation tasks.

Task description and application scenarios

Briefly describe the application scenarios for the tasks in the challenge.

A critical previous step to any surgical intervention meant to remove PDAC lesions is an accurate analysis of vascular involvement, e.g. the proportion of cancer that has invaded surrounding arteries and veins. Depending on the degree of invasion, clinicians can decide to conduct a surgical procedure on the patient or switch to other treatment courses. Because of this, there is the need to be aware of the underlying ambiguity behind PDAC segmentation, in particular in relation to vascular regions.

FURTHER INFORMATION FOR CONFERENCE ORGANIZERS

Workshop

If the challenge is part of a workshop, please indicate the workshop.

N/A

Duration

How long does the challenge take?

2 Hours

In case you selected half or full day, please explain why you need a long slot for your challenge.

N/A

Expected number of participants

Please explain the basis of your estimate (e.g. numbers from previous challenges) and/or provide a list of potential participants and indicate if they have already confirmed their willingness to contribute.

In the previous edition of the CURVAS challenge (<https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/>) there were 72 registered participants. There were 14 submissions on the validation phase, and 10 on the testing phase. Regarding the data, the CURVAS dataset had close to 500 downloads, which is directly comparable to relevant challenges such as QUBIQ2021 (<https://qubiq.grand-challenge.org/statistics/>).

This shows that there is interest in the MICCAI community to participate in competitions related to uncertainty quantification in complex segmentation tasks. We will also reach out to our past-edition challenge participants, and work on improving the baseline model in order to lower the entry barrier to the competition, thereby including as many new participants as possible.

Publication and future plans

Please indicate if you plan to coordinate a publication of the challenge results.

The first step will be to publish a paper together with the winning authors as well as making public all the code used by anyone involved in this publication. We will also analyze the combination of algorithms through ensembling, inter-algorithm variability, common issues or biases present in the submitted methods, and the variability of rankings. Our intention is to publish this analysis in a leading journal within the field of medical image analysis.

Also, the winners of the challenge will be invited to present their methods and results in the challenge event hosted in MICCAI 2025. Furthermore, the data will remain open for researchers to use it freely, always referencing the challenge.

Space and hardware requirements

Organizers of on-site challenges must provide a fair computing environment for all participants. For instance, algorithms should run on the same computing platform provided to all.

Projectors, loud speakers and microphones.

TASK 1: Calibrated Segmentation, Volume Estimation and Cardiovascular Invasion of PDAC lesions

SUMMARY

Abstract

Provide a summary of the challenge purpose. This should include a general introduction in the topic from both a biomedical as well as from a technical point of view and clearly state the envisioned technical and/or biomedical impact of the challenge.

In medical imaging, DL models are often tasked with delineating structures or abnormalities within complex anatomical structures, such as tumors, blood vessels, or organs. Uncertainty arises from the inherent complexity and variability of these structures, leading to challenges in precisely defining their boundaries. This uncertainty is further compounded by interrater variability, as different medical experts may have varying opinions on where the true boundaries lie. DL models must grapple with these discrepancies, leading to inconsistencies in segmentation results across different annotators and potentially impacting diagnosis and treatment decisions. Addressing interrater variability in DL for medical segmentation involves the development of robust algorithms capable of capturing and quantifying uncertainty, as well as standardizing annotation practices and promoting collaboration among medical experts to reduce variability and improve the reliability of DL-based medical image analysis. Interrater variability poses significant challenges in the field of DL for medical image segmentation.

This challenge is designed to promote awareness of the impact uncertainty has on clinical applications of medical image analysis. In our last-year edition, we proposed a competition based on modeling the uncertainty of segmenting three abdominal organs, namely kidney, liver and pancreas, focusing on organ volume as a clinical quantity of interest. This year, we go one step further and propose to segment pancreatic pathological structures, namely Pancreatic Ductal Adenocarcinoma (PDAC), with the clinical goal of understanding vascular involvement, a key measure of tumor resectability. In this above context, uncertainty quantification is a much more challenging task, given the wildly varying contours that different PDAC instances show.

This year, we will provide a richer dataset, in which we start from an already existing dataset of clinically verified contrast-enhanced abdominal CT scans with a single set of manual annotations (provided by the PANORAMA organization, which we invite to be part of our challenge), and make an effort to construct four extra manual annotations per PDAC case. In this way, we will assemble a unique dataset that creates a notable opportunity to analyze the impact of multi-rater annotations in several dimensions, e.g. different annotation protocols or different annotator experiences, to name a few.

Keywords

List the primary keywords that characterize the task.

N/A

ORGANIZATION

Organizers

a) Provide information on the organizing team (names and affiliations).

Meritxell Riera i Marín

Affiliation: Sycai Medical / Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF)

Title: PhD Candidate

Javier García López

Affiliation: Sycai Medical

Title: CTO and co-founder PhD

Júlia Rodríguez Comas

Affiliation: Sycai Medical

Title: CSO and co-founder PhD

Adrian Galdrán

Affiliation: Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF)

Title: Post-doc researcher, PhD

Miguel Angel González-Ballester

Affiliation: Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF)

Title: ICREA Professor, PhD

Matthias May

Affiliation: Universitätsklinikum Erlangen

Title: MD

Natália Alves,

Affiliation: Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre

Megan Schuurmans

Affiliation: Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre

Henkjan Huisman

Affiliation: Radboud University Nijmegen Medical Centre

b) Provide information on the primary contact person.

Meritxell Riera i Marín

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Life cycle type

Define the intended submission cycle of the challenge. Include information on whether/how the challenge will be continued after the challenge has taken place. Not every challenge closes after the submission deadline (one-time event). Sometimes it is possible to submit results after the deadline (open call) or the challenge is repeated with some modifications (repeated event).

Examples:

- One-time event with fixed conference submission deadline
- Open call (challenge opens for new submissions after conference deadline)
- Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Repeated event with annual fixed conference submission deadline

Challenge venue and platform

a) Report the event (e.g. conference) that is associated with the challenge (if any).

MICCAI 2025

Our goal is to establish annual editions of the challenge, each exploring new approaches to understanding and leveraging interrater variability in the context of pancreatic image analysis. This variability is an inherent and pervasive feature across many areas of medical imaging. Rather than attempting to reduce or eliminate it, we aim to harness it as valuable information. By doing so, we aspire to create a benchmark challenge that serves as a reference for addressing and utilizing these concepts and challenges in the future.

b) Report the platform (e.g. grand-challenge.org) used to run the challenge.

grand-challenge.org

c) Provide the URL for the challenge website (if any).

This is last year's website <https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/>, and our goal is to keep expanding it and improving it with the new editions.

Participation policies

a) Define the allowed user interaction of the algorithms assessed (e.g. only (semi-) automatic methods allowed).

Fully automatic

b) Define the policy on the usage of training data. The data used to train algorithms may, for example, be restricted to the data provided by the challenge or to publicly available data including (open) pre-trained nets.

Publicly available data is allowed. Our data consists of multiple re-annotations of a subset of the PANORAMA dataset. Specifically, we adopt CT scans that were introduced for the PANORAMA competition for the first time, and we request the participants not to use this subset for training, as they might be inadvertently using CT scans that will appear in the test set (although with multiple, unseen annotations). PANORAMA also subsumed other public datasets, which are allowed in this competition.

c) Define the participation policy for members of the organizers' institutes. For example, members of the organizers' institutes may participate in the challenge but are not eligible for awards.

May participate but not eligible for awards (they may be listed in the leaderboard).

d) Define the award policy. In particular, provide details with respect to challenge prizes.

First prize: 1000€

Second prize: 500€

Third prize: 250€

e) Define the policy for result announcement.

Examples:

- Top 3 performing methods will be announced publicly.
- Participating teams can choose whether the performance results will be made public.

Top five performing methods will be announced publicly.

f) Define the publication policy. In particular, provide details on ...

- ... who of the participating teams/the participating teams' members qualifies as author
- ... whether the participating teams may publish their own results separately, and (if so)
- ... whether an embargo time is defined (so that challenge organizers can publish a challenge paper first).

Three members of the participating team can be qualified as author (the person that submits the results). The participating team may publish their own results separately only after the organizer has published a challenge paper and always mentioning the organizer's challenge paper.

Submission method

a) Describe the method used for result submission. Preferably, provide a link to the submission instructions.

Examples:

- Docker container on the Synapse platform. Link to submission instructions: <URL>
- Algorithm output was sent to organizers via e-mail. Submission instructions were sent by e-mail.

The challenge will have two phases, Validation and Testing. In the Validation phase participants will create docker containers and submit them wrapped as algorithms to Grand-Challenge. This process will allow participants to both measure performance on a small subset of the test set and debug their Docker containers. The Testing phase will follow a similar procedure: participants will submit their algorithms in the form of a Docker container with a short abstract highlighting the contributions. A baseline model and working docker container will be made available shortly after the start of the competition. Furthermore, an extra phase will be created to let the participants test with few training data their algorithms. This Sanity Check phase is open for everyone to see how their algorithms perform and, if needed, do some fixes.

Participants will be asked to open-source their solutions after the end of the challenge to ensure reproducibility, as well as indicate the versions of the different libraries used as well. Participants are required to share their source code under an open-source license, such as the MIT License. This license should grant the Organizer the right to distribute the code publicly for research and development purposes. While participants maintain copyright ownership of their submitted code, failure to specify a license will result in the assumption that the MIT License applies. By submitting without explicit licensing information, participants acknowledge and affirm that they possess all necessary rights to permit such submission under the MIT License.

Once the challenge is finished and the winners are announced, they will be asked to publicly share their code and model and, until the first dissemination paper is published, reproducibility checks will be performed in order to evaluate the quality of the results. However, regardless of the quality of the code, the main focus will be set on whether the results are reproducible or not.

b) Provide information on the possibility for participating teams to evaluate their algorithms before submitting final results. For example, many challenges allow submission of multiple results, and only the last run is officially counted to compute challenge results.

Participants will be allowed to submit 3 times during validation and twice for the Testing phase - only the best submission will be considered. For checking whether their algorithm works, they will have the Sanity Check phase open during the whole challenge.

Challenge schedule

Provide a timetable for the challenge. Preferably, this should include

- the release date(s) of the training cases (if any)
- the registration date/period
- the release date(s) of the test cases and validation cases (if any)
- the submission date(s)
- associated workshop days (if any)
- the release date(s) of the results

Challenge website open: April 1st 2025

Registration date: April 1st 2025

Training set release: May 1st 2025

Validation submission open: June 15th 2025

Test submission open: July 28th 2025

Release date of the results: August 15th 2025

Challenge days (MICCAI): September 23rd-27th 2025

Ethics approval

Indicate whether ethics approval is necessary for the data. If yes, provide details on the ethics approval, preferably institutional review board, location, date and number of the ethics approval (if applicable). Add the URL or a reference to the document of the ethics approval (if available).

The original CT scans used for this challenge is a subset of the PANORAMA dataset (<https://panorama.grand-challenge.org/>), which we reannotate multiple times. We have discussed with the PANORAMA organization the use of their dataset, and also invited them to be part of our organization. Therefore, there is full permission to use this dataset, and there is no ethics approval needed.

Data usage agreement

Clarify how the data can be used and distributed by the teams that participate in the challenge and by others during and after the challenge. This should include the explicit listing of the license applied.

Examples:

- CC BY (Attribution)
- CC BY-SA (Attribution-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-ND (Attribution-NoDerivs)
- CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)
- CC BY-NC-SA (Attribution-NonCommercial-ShareAlike)
- CC BY-NC-ND (Attribution-NonCommercial-NoDerivs)

CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial)

Code availability

a) Provide information on the accessibility of the organizers' evaluation software (e.g. code to produce rankings). Preferably, provide a link to the code and add information on the supported platforms.

The code to produce rankings will be released together with the training data.

b) In an analogous manner, provide information on the accessibility of the participating teams' code.

The participants will have to submit their models in Docker containers during the test phase. The procedure to create the Docker containers will be given beforehand, as well as the recommended version to be used.

Conflicts of interest

Provide information related to conflicts of interest. In particular provide information related to sponsoring/funding of the challenge. Also, state explicitly who had/will have access to the test case labels and when.

There is no conflict of interest to be reported. The funding of the challenge is done by the organizers. The participants will not have access to the test case labels until after the challenge is closed.

MISSION OF THE CHALLENGE

Field(s) of application

State the main field(s) of application that the participating algorithms target.

Examples:

- Diagnosis
- Education
- Intervention assistance
- Intervention follow-up
- Intervention planning
- Prognosis

- Research
- Screening
- Training
- Cross-phase

Research, Decision support, Intervention planning

Task category(ies)

State the task category(ies)

Examples:

- Classification
- Detection
- Localization
- Modeling
- Prediction
- Reconstruction
- Registration
- Retrieval
- Segmentation
- Tracking

Segmentation, Calibration, Uncertainty, Volume assessment

Cohorts

We distinguish between the target cohort and the challenge cohort. For example, a challenge could be designed around the task of medical instrument tracking in robotic kidney surgery. While the challenge could be based on ex vivo data obtained from a laparoscopic training environment with porcine organs (challenge cohort), the final biomedical application (i.e. robotic kidney surgery) would be targeted on real patients with certain characteristics defined by inclusion criteria such as restrictions regarding sex or age (target cohort).

a) Describe the target cohort, i.e. the subjects/objects from whom/which the data would be acquired in the final biomedical application.

The target cohort for this challenge comprises clinicians tasked with determining whether a patient with PDAC meets the criteria to proceed with surgical intervention. The aim is to leverage multi-rater information to identify ambiguous regions of the PDAC, ensuring these areas are considered when evaluating the lesion's volume or its potential cardiovascular invasion prior to surgery.

This challenge focuses on PDAC, the most common and aggressive type of pancreatic cancer, which is neither effectively preventable nor screenable and is associated with a devastating 98% loss in life expectancy. However,

the framework of this challenge will be adaptable to other cancers or lesions that share similar surgical decision-making criteria.

b) Describe the challenge cohort, i.e. the subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the challenge data was acquired.

The challenge cohort will comprise 125 CT scans selected from a subset of the PANORAMA challenge dataset. The selection process will prioritize CT scans with manually generated labels, excluding those with automatically derived annotations. Additionally, only cases with a conclusive diagnostic test (e.g., pathology, cytology, histopathology) will be included, while patients with radiology-based diagnoses will be excluded.

To ensure the subset is representative of common real-world scenarios, lesion sizes will be analyzed, and a diverse range of cases will be selected. Furthermore, patient demographics, including sex and age, will be considered to enhance the cohort's representativeness.

Finally, a preliminary visual analysis is conducted before sending the image to radiologists for segmentation. This ensures the tumor's location, size, and relevance, helping maintain the dataset's representativeness for the challenge.

Imaging modality(ies)

Specify the imaging technique(s) applied in the challenge.

The PANORAMA data set consists of a retrospective, multi-center, cancer-enriched set of routing abdominal and upper-abdominal Axial, portal-venous CECT scans.

Context information

Provide additional information given along with the images. The information may correspond ...

a) ... directly to the image data (e.g. tumor volume).

The information about the invasion of the PDAC into the vascular structures will be released as well.

b) ... to the patient in general (e.g. sex, medical history).

No other information that is not already public about the patient will be released since the CT images and their corresponding information are already publicly available.

Target entity(ies)

a) Describe the data origin, i.e. the region(s)/part(s) of subject(s)/object(s) from whom/which the image data would be acquired in the final biomedical application (e.g. brain shown in computed tomography (CT) data, abdomen shown in laparoscopic video data, operating room shown in video data, thorax shown in fluoroscopy video). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

Pancreas shown in Contrast-Enhanced Computed Tomography.

b) Describe the algorithm target, i.e. the structure(s)/subject(s)/object(s)/component(s) that the participating algorithms have been designed to focus on (e.g. tumor in the brain, tip of a medical instrument, nurse in an operating theater, catheter in a fluoroscopy scan). If necessary, differentiate between target and challenge cohort.

The algorithm target will be the PDAC. However, other structures will be annotated since they are needed to do the assessment (pancreas and cardiovascular structures).

Assessment aim(s)

Identify the property(ies) of the algorithms to be optimized to perform well in the challenge. If multiple properties are assessed, prioritize them (if appropriate). The properties should then be reflected in the metrics applied (see below, parameter metric(s)), and the priorities should be reflected in the ranking when combining multiple metrics that assess different properties.

- Example 1: Find highly accurate liver segmentation algorithm for CT images.
- Example 2: Find lung tumor detection algorithm with high sensitivity and specificity for mammography images.

Corresponding metrics are listed below (parameter metric(s)).

Well-performing algorithms will produce PDAC segmentations with ambiguous zones similar to those of human annotators. Vascular involvement of the segmented lesions should correlate well with vascular involvement as computed from manual annotations, including variability. Similar considerations apply to lesion load/volume.

DATA SETS

Data source(s)

a) Specify the device(s) used to acquire the challenge data. This includes details on the device(s) used to acquire the imaging data (e.g. manufacturer) as well as information on additional devices used for performance assessment (e.g. tracking system used in a surgical setting).

The scanners used for the PANORAMA datasets are: TOSHIBA, Philips, SIEMENS, GE MEDICAL SYSTEMS and Canon Medical Systems.

b) Describe relevant details on the imaging process/data acquisition for each acquisition device (e.g. image acquisition protocol(s)).

All images are CECT scans in the portal-venous phase. All exams are from patients undergoing CECT without a history of pancreatic cancer treatment, and without any prior positive PDAC histopathology findings.

c) Specify the center(s)/institute(s) in which the data was acquired and/or the data providing platform/source (e.g. previous challenge). If this information is not provided (e.g. for anonymization reasons), specify why.

They belong to at least two centers in The Netherlands (Radboud University Medical Center (RUMC) and University Medical Center Groningen (UMCG)), one center in Norway (Helse Bergen HF Haukeland University Hospital (HUH)), and one center in Sweden (Karolinska Institute (KSKI)). The data in the PANORAMA challenge that belongs to other public datasets will not be considered.

d) Describe relevant characteristics (e.g. level of expertise) of the subjects (e.g. surgeon)/objects (e.g. robot) involved in the data acquisition process (if any).

The data acquisition was performed by experts from the PANORAMA working group. The subset selected from there will follow the following criteria:

- Only CTs with manually generated labels will be considered.
- Only CTs with conclusive diagnostic tests will be included (e.g. pathology, cytology, histopathology and cytology).
- The size of the lesions will be analyzed and a subset will be selected.
- For the final bias analysis, factors such as devices, sex, and patient age will be considered to improve the cohort's representativeness. Efforts will be made to balance bias as evenly as possible across these variables. For age distribution, the target percentages are as follows: below 50 years (5%), 50–59 years (15%), 60–69 years (20%),

70–79 years (30%), and 80–89 years (30%) (1,2,3,4). While these percentages are approximate and have been rounded for simplicity, the balance will aim to be as close to these proportions as feasible. For the sex, 40-50% for females and 50-60% for males (5). For location of the PDAC, 60-70% head, 15-25% body and 10-15% tail (6).

Training and test case characteristics

a) State what is meant by one case in this challenge. A case encompasses all data that is processed to produce one result that is compared to the corresponding reference result (i.e. the desired algorithm output).

Examples:

- Training and test cases both represent a CT image of a human brain. Training cases have a weak annotation (tumor present or not and tumor volume (if any)) while the test cases are annotated with the tumor contour (if any).
- A case refers to all information that is available for one particular patient in a specific study. This information always includes the image information as specified in data source(s) (see above) and may include context information (see above). Both training and test cases are annotated with survival (binary) 5 years after (first) image was taken.

All the data provided in this challenge are CT images of a human abdomen. Each CT will have five different PDAC annotations: one from the PANORAMA expert and four more from other experts from three different hospitals (Universitätsklinikum Erlangen, Hospital de Sant Pau, Hospital de Mataró). Furthermore, the other labels from the PANORAMA dataset (veins, arteries and pancreas) will be used since they are needed to assess some of the parameters being evaluated in this challenge.

b) State the total number of training, validation and test cases.

The dataset consists of 125 abdominal CTs with five PDAC segmentations. It will be splitted in three different subsets:

- For the training set, 40 images will be used.
- For the validation set, 5 images will be used.
- For the testing set, 80 images will be used.

c) Explain why a total number of cases and the specific proportion of training, validation and test cases was chosen.

While 125 CTs is neither a small nor a large dataset, careful allocation is essential. For the validation set, only 5 images are used to maximize the number of images available for the testing set. At the same time, a sufficient number of images is allocated to the training set, with 40 images designated for this purpose.

Moreover, the dataset offers flexibility for expansion by incorporating additional publicly available data (except the PANORAMA data that coming from Batch 1 (<https://zenodo.org/records/13715870>), Batch 2 (<https://zenodo.org/records/13742336>), and Batch 3 (<https://zenodo.org/records/11034011>)), allowing it to grow into a larger resource. Batch 4 (<https://zenodo.org/records/10999754>) of the PANORAMA dataset can be used.

d) Mention further important characteristics of the training, validation and test cases (e.g. class distribution in classification tasks chosen according to real-world distribution vs. equal class distribution) and justify the choice.

For selecting the 125 CTs from the PANORAMA dataset different criteria will be considered. As previously indicated, the first filtering criteria will be manual annotations and having a conclusive diagnostic test. Afterwards, we will try to balance equally the sex and the hardware from which the CT comes from. Finally, the age

distribution will be considered.

e) Challenge organizers are encouraged to (partly) use unseen, unpublished data for their challenges. Describe if new data will be used for the challenge and state the number of cases along with the proportion of new data.

There will not be unpublished CT images, since we will be using the PANORAMA cases. However, we will provide four new annotations from different experts and backgrounds that will enrich this subset and allow us to understand and model interrater variability challenges.

Annotation characteristics

a) Describe the method for determining the reference annotation, i.e. the desired algorithm output. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Possible methods include manual image annotation, in silico ground truth generation and annotation by automatic methods.

If human annotation was involved, state the number of annotators.

For each scan, there will be four new annotations provided from four different experts from three different institutions.

b) Provide the instructions given to the annotators (if any) prior to the annotation. This may include description of a training phase with the software. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary. Preferably, provide a link to the annotation protocol.

Only the CECT scan will be provided to the annotators. They will know that there is a PDAC but not where. The other labels being used will be kept from the annotators since we prefer to avoid supplying extra information that may generate biases between them.

c) Provide details on the subject(s)/algorithm(s) that annotated the cases (e.g. information on level of expertise such as number of years of professional experience, medically-trained or not). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The four radiologists that participate have the following experience: 22 years of expertise, 7 years of expertise, 3 years of expertise and 1 year of expertise.

d) Describe the method(s) used to merge multiple annotations for one case (if any). Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

No label merging will occur, since we are precisely interested in measuring and modeling inter-annotator variability.

Data pre-processing method(s)

Describe the method(s) used for pre-processing the raw training data before it is provided to the participating teams. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases if necessary.

The studies included in the training, validation and testing datasets were downloaded from the PANORAMA database, which it is already preprocessed and ready for use.

Sources of error

a) Describe the most relevant possible error sources related to the image annotation. If possible, estimate the magnitude (range) of these errors, using inter-and intra-annotator variability, for example. Provide the information separately for the training, validation and test cases, if necessary.

First of all, it is important to stress that we will be working with an already controlled environment. Regarding the quality and processing of the images it has already been conducted by the organizers of the PANORAMA challenge, which is already an important step towards avoiding possible errors. Regarding errors related to the image annotation process, this is actually why we propose to work with multiple annotators. We do not consider and approach variability among clinicians as something we need to deal with and fix, but as extra information that can enrich our models and our evaluations. In medical imaging, there is the inherent ambiguity of the image that cannot be reduced (aleatoric uncertainty). In the edges of the structures there are always going to be different considerations on what belongs or not to the structure due to the blurriness and maybe low quality of the image we could be working with. It is almost impossible to eliminate inter-rater variability and we should not do it, since it gives us information about more complex cases and how to approach ambiguous areas or challenging images.

However, a problem that could emerge in our context is that this phenomenon inadvertently creates a bias among raters. This is why our final choice was to give only the CT image and let them know that there is a PDAC but nothing else. This way, the bias will be reduced as much as possible, since we are not giving extra information (such as demographic information or other annotations) that could influence the annotation.

b) In an analogous manner, describe and quantify other relevant sources of error.

One of the relevant sources of error is the image quality and the complexity of the structure being labeled, which in our case is high. On the other hand, we tried to reduce as possible the potential interrater variability (i.e. avoid too large variations) by simplifying and reducing the amount of structures to label (just the PDAC) and not add entropy by incorporating extra information, such as demographic data or other annotations, e.g. veins. Nonetheless, there is a human variability that cannot and should not be ignored. This is why, in this challenge, we highlight the importance of studying these areas in which there is ambiguity that cannot be eliminated. In order to keep improving the dataset, we will establish a GitHub repository to solicit possible errors from data users.

ASSESSMENT METHODS

Metric(s)

a) Define the metric(s) to assess a property of an algorithm. These metrics should reflect the desired algorithm properties described in assessment aim(s) (see above). State which metric(s) were used to compute the ranking(s) (if any).

- Example 1: Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC)
- Example 2: Area under curve (AUC)

As indicated in (8) it is not trivial to define an evaluation criteria that reflects the biomedical need. Although overlap measures of segmentation quality must and will be adopted, we highlight that the Dice Similarity Score (DSC) is often used without considering the fact that there are small structures that should be analysed otherwise. As the QUBIQ challenge states: "Dice scores have many shortcomings, in particular in the novel application domain of uncertainty-aware image quantification." Consequently, additional metrics will be considered to have a proper and thorough assessment as well as clinically relevant.

In this study, DSC will be applied with specific considerations. Given that most structures in our case are small, DSC must be treated with caution and adapted to these structures. From a clinical standpoint, an algorithm that

identifies all structures of interest (e.g., tumors) is far more valuable than one achieving high accuracy on a single structure but failing to detect others (9). However, since our dataset includes only one PDAC per CT scan, the risk of missed detections is mitigated. To further refine the DSC for small structures, we will use an adapted version that emphasizes edge regions. Additionally, given the presence of interrater variability, DSC calculations will focus exclusively on consensus areas—regions unanimously labeled as part of the structure by all raters. Dissensus areas, where there is disagreement among raters, will not be included in the computation of the DSC. Instead, these regions require alternative evaluation approaches, as no clear ground truth exists for binarization or adjudication (see <https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/metrics-and-evaluation/#1-quality-of-the-segmentation-and-uncertainty-consensus-assessment>).

To enhance clinical relevance, we will analyze key biomarkers, such as volume and vascular involvement. Volume will be assessed separately for consensus and dissensus areas. Consensus volumes, derived from the intersection of annotations from all raters, will include an uncertainty evaluation, aiming for near-zero uncertainty (see <https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/metrics-and-evaluation/#1-quality-of-the-segmentation-and-uncertainty-consensus-assessment>). For a more nuanced evaluation, the Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS) will be employed to assess the computed volume of each PDAC, incorporating all annotation data (see <https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/metrics-and-evaluation/#3-volume-assessment>).

A second component of the challenge will evaluate model calibration. Multiclass and multi-rater calibration is inherently complex, but our aim is to define metrics that are both clear and intuitive. For this, we will use the multi-rater Expected Calibration Error (ECE) introduced in the previous edition of the challenge (see <https://curvas.grand-challenge.org/metrics-and-evaluation/#2-multi-rater-calibration>). This metric evaluates calibration across different annotations from all raters, treating them separately.

This year's challenge introduces the additional complexity of determining whether a PDAC invades vascular structures. We will build on the methodology proposed in (10), adapting it to align with our criteria and conditions. Vascular involvement variability will be analyzed with confidence intervals and statistically rigorous measures. Radiologists will also provide insights and clinical information, ensuring the results are clinically meaningful.

All the annotations of each image will be used for the evaluation, since interrater variability must be considered as well for the performance assessment of the algorithm. By combining these approaches, this challenge aims to deliver robust, clinically relevant assessments that address the unique challenges of PDAC evaluation.

b) Justify why the metric(s) was/were chosen, preferably with reference to the biomedical application.

In this challenge, we are looking to develop a way to study not only the performance of a Neural Network, but how calibrated it is as well as define a metric to assess its clinical value. Since we are trying to work in a scope as close to the real world as possible, we are dealing with multi rater variability; there will be five annotations for each lesion defined by five different radiologists. Interrater variability is something that is not going to disappear due to, for example, the inherent variability of the image itself, hence, we believe that we need to accept it and attempt to model it. For this reason, the different regions of study will be split in three: the consensus background area, the dissensus area which can belong both to the background or the structure and, the consensus foreground area, which will be defined by the region that can only belong to the organ without any ambiguity.

Furthermore, generally there is a lack of connection between the technical side and the clinical relevance of the different algorithms that are developed. Because of that, the first part of evaluating the algorithms will be

focusing on developing a relevant way of giving information to the radiologists or oncologists. This is why biomarkers such as volume and vascular invasion are considered relevant for the assessment of this challenge. However, interrater variability will not be eliminated but rather modeled and quantified. Hence, the different volume assessments and the vascular invasion will be approached carefully. In addition, we find it interesting to have a classical technical assessment as well. Consequently, we consider that both an adaptation of DSC and volume are complementary and relevant since it is a way to study how the model is working in a classical way as well as in a clinical context.

The justification for considering both calibration and uncertainty assessment lies in their complementary roles in providing a holistic evaluation of a predictive model. For the calibration, we will be using an adaptation to the multi annotator of the classic Expected Calibration Error (ECE) to measure the discrepancy between predicted probabilities and observed outcomes, providing insight into model calibration. Meanwhile, uncertainty assessment evaluates the model's confidence in predictions. Together, they offer a comprehensive view, ensuring not only accurate calibration but also a robust understanding of the model's uncertainty, enhancing the overall reliability and effectiveness of the predictive system.

Ranking method(s)

a) Describe the method used to compute a performance rank for all submitted algorithms based on the generated metric results on the test cases. Typically the text will describe how results obtained per case and metric are aggregated to arrive at a final score/ranking.

We will employ multiple evaluation metrics, culminating in a merged ranking (8). These metrics are designed to capture both segmentation accuracy and clinical relevance while addressing the inherent complexities of multi-rater annotations and vascular invasion.

- Adapted DSC: An adapted version of the Dice Similarity Coefficient (DSC) will be the primary metric for segmentation evaluation. This adaptation accounts for the small size of the structures and emphasizes edge regions, providing more robust rankings compared to the Hausdorff Distance (HD) (7).
- Volume Assessment with CRPS: To enhance clinical relevance, the volume of the parenchyma will also be evaluated. Given the presence of multiple annotations, this volume will be assessed using the Continuous Ranked Probability Score (CRPS) to incorporate all annotation data.
- Uncertainty of Consensus Volume: The volume assessment will be complemented by an uncertainty metric, quantifying the reliability of the consensus volume. Since this volume is derived from the intersection of all annotations, its uncertainty should ideally be close to zero.
- Multi-Rater ECE: For calibration, an adapted version of the Expected Calibration Error (ECE) will be used. This adaptation is specifically designed to handle multi-rater annotations, ensuring accurate calibration assessment across all annotations.
- Vessel Involvement Quantifier: To evaluate vascular invasion, a dedicated quantifier will be employed. This metric will assess the extent of vessel involvement, leveraging clinical insights and expert annotations to ensure robust results.

The final ranking will be determined through mean and metric-based aggregation, ensuring that multiple sub-rankings are considered by averaging their contributions. To assess the stability of this ranking, bootstrap resampling with 1,000 iterations will be performed, allowing for an evaluation of its robustness across different

dataset variations. Finally, the Wilcoxon signed-rank test will be applied for pairwise comparisons of algorithms across each metric, providing statistical confirmation of the ranking by analyzing the significance of differences within individual sub-rankings.

b) Describe the method(s) used to manage submissions with missing results on test cases.

Missing results on the submissions will be scored as 0.

Even though assigning a score of 0 to the missing results may be unfair in close competition scenarios, we do not find a better way to assess these results. Participants should take time on studying if they have all the results needed. Furthermore, they will have a Sanity Check Phase always open to check for errors in their algorithms and for the validation phase they will have several attempts to submit their results so they can check and understand the procedure. In addition, for the testing phase they will have two attempts and only the best submission will be considered, giving them an advantage if any of the submissions have a missing result.

c) Justify why the described ranking scheme(s) was/were used.

This ranking system is designed to consider essential metrics individually in the processes of segmentation, calibration, and uncertainty assessment. Additionally, it aims to assess the overall performance of participant teams. To ensure a comprehensive evaluation for the different capabilities, we recommend the use of multiple metrics to avoid bias and discourage teams from optimizing their methods solely for a particular performance metric. To compute the final ranking, the average of the rankings of the different metrics will be considered.

Statistical analysis will be conducted to validate the ranking outcomes. The selection of statistical methods, including bootstrap and the Wilcoxon test, for ranking submissions is underpinned by their suitability for the challenge's data characteristics and objectives. Bootstrap resampling allows for robust estimation of uncertainty in metrics, crucial in evaluating diverse submissions across various metrics. The Wilcoxon test offers a non-parametric approach to compare performances, ensuring fair evaluation regardless of metric variations. Together, these methods provide a rigorous and unbiased framework for ranking submissions, aligning with the challenge's objective of impartially assessing diverse model performances.

Statistical analyses

a) Provide details for the statistical methods used in the scope of the challenge analysis. This may include

- description of the missing data handling,
- details about the assessment of variability of rankings,
- description of any method used to assess whether the data met the assumptions, required for the particular statistical approach, or
- indication of any software product that was used for all data analysis methods.

In instances of missing data or reporting errors, organizers are tasked with assisting participants in rectifying and completing the missing results initially. For incomplete test cases, scores will be designated as 0. As already said, participants should take time on studying if they have all the results needed. Furthermore, they will have a Sanity Check Phase always open to check for errors in their algorithms and for the validation phase they will have several attempts to submit their results so they can check and understand the procedure. In addition, for the testing phase they will have two attempts and only the best submission will be considered, giving them an advantage if any of the submissions have a missing result.

b) Justify why the described statistical method(s) was/were used.

The devised ranking scheme deliberately steers clear of favoring a single metric that might outperform other methods. Instead, it prioritizes metrics aligned with medical requirements and substantial clinical significance. As a result, various evaluation metrics from different perspectives are incorporated. The statistical analysis focuses on methods consistently ranked higher across multiple metrics, providing a deeper scrutiny of the ranking outcomes.

The selection of statistical methods, including bootstrap and the Wilcoxon test, for ranking submissions is underpinned by their suitability for the challenge's data characteristics and objectives. Bootstrap resampling allows for robust estimation of uncertainty in metrics, crucial in evaluating diverse submissions across various metrics. The Wilcoxon test offers a non-parametric approach to compare performances, ensuring fair evaluation regardless of metric variations. Together, these methods provide a rigorous and unbiased framework for ranking submissions, aligning with the challenge's objective of impartially assessing diverse model performances.

Further analyses

Present further analyses to be performed (if applicable), e.g. related to

- combining algorithms via ensembling,
- inter-algorithm variability,
- common problems/biases of the submitted methods, or
- ranking variability.

The first step will be to publish a paper together with the winning authors as well as making public all the code used by anyone involved in the publication. In the future, we plan to analyze the combination of algorithms through ensembling, inter-algorithm variability, common issues or biases present in the submitted methods, and the variability rankings. Our intention is to publish this analysis in a leading journal within the field of medical image analysis.

Also, the winners of the challenge will be invited to present their methods and results in the challenge event hosted in MICCAI 2025. Furthermore, the data will remain open for researchers to use it freely, always referencing the challenge.

ADDITIONAL POINTS

References

Please include any reference important for the challenge design, for example publications on the data, the annotation process or the chosen metrics as well as DOIs referring to data or code.

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(8) Maier-Hein, Lena, et al. "Metrics Reloaded: Recommendations for Image Analysis Validation" (Version 7). arXiv:2206.01653 [cs.CV]. 2022. Web. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2206.01653>

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Further comments

Further comments from the organizers.

All data usage from the PANORAMA challenge has been requested and approved by the organizers in advance, who have been invited to this challenge organization.